

Factors Influencing Employee Service Performance in the Malaysian Healthcare Industry

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Abstract:

The healthcare industry is one of the fastest-growing industry in the world. It is an essential industry providing services to patients, families and communities. Furthermore, the healthcare industry directly affects individuals' health by providing essential services like medical care, preventive measures, and treatment for illnesses and injuries. Hence, it is important to ensure that the healthcare industry continues to provide excellent services to communities. The healthcare industry relies on employee services as high-performing employees provide better patient care, which is essential for effective treatment, recovery, and overall patient satisfaction. Competent and empathetic staff can make a significant difference in patient outcomes. In Malaysia, employee service performance is a driving force boosting the Malaysian Medical tourism. As such, the purpose of this research was to study the influence of factors such as teamwork, training, working environment and performance appraisal on employee service performance in the Malaysia healthcare industry. The aim of the research was to study the possible influence that these factors have on employee service performance in the Malaysia healthcare industry. The study used a deductive approach with questionnaires distributed online to 200 employees in the Malaysian healthcare industry working in hospitals and clinics in the states of Penang and Selangor, Malaysia. SPSS was used to conduct the data analysis and in studying the relationships between teamwork, training, working environment and performance appraisal with employee service performance in the Malaysian healthcare industry. The results of the study revealed that teamwork, training and working environment have significant positive relationships with employee service performance in the Malaysian healthcare industry. The findings of this research revealed that the healthcare industry would benefit from the service of employees if the healthcare industry provides necessary training needed to enhance the skills of employees, fosters teamwork for better integration across various functions and improves the working environment of employees for mental health and well-being, which are the scientific novelty of this study. Implications of the research findings are presented as well.

Keywords (in English): employee service performance, teamwork, training, working environment, performance appraisal

1. Introduction

A service is an intangible action or activity provided by the service provider to the service recipient or customer in exchange for a fee, payment, or other worth. Service performance is the outcome of an individual's effort and seriousness in completing a task entrusted with the knowledge, expertise, and sincerity in line with the duties and responsibilities assigned to particular individual (Niati, 2021). The term "healthcare industry" on the other hand refers to a group of organizations facilities, and individuals who work in the delivery of medical supplies and services to people and communities for the purpose of identifying, managing, and preventing disease, injury, and illness as well as enhancing general health and wellbeing (Riley et al, 2019). Hospitals, clinics, nursing homes, pharmacies, pharmaceutical and governmental organizations involved in healthcare policy and regulation are just a few of the many activities and sectors that make up the healthcare industry. Various healthcare workers are also

included in it, including doctors, nurses, pharmacists, therapists, and other allied health professionals. Service performance of healthcare industry and the quality of care delivered in medical facilities are strongly related. Healthcare professionals must deliver prompt, efficient, and compassionate treatment to patients. Healthcare organizations can find gaps in care delivery and make the required adjustments by analyzing service performance to guarantee that patients receive high-quality care (Ferreira & Marques, 2021). The operational effectiveness of healthcare organizations may be influenced by employee service performance. Healthcare organizations can analyze service performance to find inefficiencies, bottlenecks, and opportunities for process improvement, which can lead to greater resource utilization, higher productivity, and cost savings (Guzzo et al, 2022). Service performance quality has a direct influence on patient satisfaction, which is important in the healthcare industry. Patients who are satisfied are more likely to follow instructions and stick to treatment regimens, which results in greater health (Afthanorhan et al, 2019). Healthcare organizations may pinpoint opportunities for development and raise patient satisfaction by understanding the elements that contribute to good service performance, which improves patient experiences and lead to good reputation and competitiveness (Asnawi et al, 2019).

Globally, the healthcare services industry in the US grew \$7,499.75 billion in 2022 to \$7,975.87 billion in 2023 at a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 6.3%. (“Healthcare Service Global Market Report”, 2023). In developing countries particularly, investing in healthcare services has had profound effect on economic development. It not only improves the health and well-being of citizens but also sets the stage for sustainable economic growth and development. As these countries continue to prioritize healthcare, they are likely to see further improvements in economic indicators and overall quality of life for their people. In Malaysia, the healthcare landscape comprises of urban-focused private providers and a public sector catering to many healthcare needs. As globalization has increased the healthcare industry in Malaysia, the Malaysia's health expenditure will grow by a 2023-2028 compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 8.3 per cent, with public expenditure growing by 8.5 per cent and private expenditure by 8.1 per cent (“Malaysia’s Health Expenditure to grow 8.3 Pcf Cagr From 2023-2028”, 2024).

Malaysia offers both public and private healthcare systems. Private healthcare providers are leading the adoption of health technology and forming partnerships with international healthcare providers to enhance their services for medical tourists. Meanwhile, public healthcare providers are expanding their capabilities in prevention, screening, and improving healthcare access in remote areas of the country. These ongoing efforts will drive demand for related technologies and products. Malaysia is famous for medical tourism; being a fertility hub, cardiology hub and cancer centre of excellence. In 2024, the Malaysian healthcare sector is set to experience continued growth, supported by a significant increase in the Health Ministry's budget allocation, enhanced cooperation between public and private sectors, and continued expansion in medical tourism (“Bigger Budget a Boon for Healthcare Sector”, 2023). Under Budget 2024, the ministry received a higher allocation of RM41.2 billion, marking a notable year-on-year increase of 13.5%. This rise in funding represents one of the largest annual increases seen in recent years. Hence, it is thus important that the service performance of the healthcare industry is enhanced to cater to the growing demand. Furthermore, empirical evidence shows that, if employees are able to deliver high-quality service, customers are more likely to generate favourable evaluations of service encounters, experience higher satisfaction, and increase their purchases and the frequency of their future visits (Rane et al, 2023)

Past studies have examined the effect of factors such as employee satisfaction, employee commitment, employee well-being, quality of care; staffing, resource adequacy, manager abilities, and support on employee service performance in the Malaysian healthcare industry (Abdullah, et al, 2021; Parashakti et al., 2023). However, there is still scarce research on the influence of teamwork, training, working environment and performance appraisal on employee service performance in the Malaysian healthcare industry. Therefore, this study aims to determine the influence of teamwork, training, working environment and performance appraisal on employee service performance of healthcare industry in Malaysia. This could help the healthcare organizations to better develop plans and strategies in order to increase the efficiency of service provided to patients and consumers. Furthermore, this research may be a reference for the improvements in the teamwork, training, working environment and performance appraisal in the future development.

According to Praba (2022) the Malaysian healthcare industry must encourage teamwork between different specialists involved in the care of the patient to improve employee service performance and subsequently provide a more holistic care. The importance of teamwork among employees in the healthcare industry can be seen from the recent Renal Nutrition Conference organized by the National Kidney Foundation Malaysia (NKF) in Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia in June 2024 aimed to underscore the importance of teamwork among healthcare professionals in improving patient care. The conference focused on engaging dietitians, nephrologists, physicians, nurses, and

pharmacists as well (Murugesan, 2024). Hence, this study would examine the influence of teamwork towards employee service performance in the Malaysian the Healthcare Industry. Furthermore, in Malaysia, the Minister of Health pledged to promptly resolve specialist-training issues and harmonise national training programmes in keeping with laws, regulations, and standards, to achieve the nation's urgent need for specialists in the medical industry. The Ministry of Health White Paper will emphasise the need to invest in the training and development of healthcare professionals, ensuring that Malaysia has skilled workforce capable of providing high-quality care and subsequently affecting employees' service performance (Chan, 2023). Vethasalam (2024) stated that with Malaysia already facing a shortage of specialist, junior doctors welcome the parallel pathway programme that would allow Malaysian healthcare professionals to seek specialist training for selected postgraduate qualifications abroad, to mitigate the shortage of specialist in Malaysia. Hence, this study would examine the influence of training towards employee service performance in the Malaysian the Healthcare Industry.

Vethasalam (2022) found that the mental health of junior doctors was severely impacted by their working environment such as long working hours, poor work-life balance, and senior doctors' bullying them. Under the condition of anonymity, young doctors asserted that the bullying culture was entrenched across the healthcare industry. In addition, junior physicians undertake many odd duties that did not help with their training, which is a concern that might have an impact on how well the healthcare organization performs overall. Some younger doctors may be required to perform seven to eight on-call tasks every month, according to a doctor in the anesthesiology department of a hospital in Kedah Malaysia leading to an effect in their service performance. On-call session could run between 24 and 28 hours, meaning that if they are required to be on-call on the weekends, they effectively do not have any days off that whole week (Vethasalam, 2022). Furthermore, following the allegations of doctor bullying and the death of a houseman in a Hospital in Malaysia, Healthcare Work Culture Improvement Task Force (HWCITF), headed by the former secretary-general of the Science, Technology and Innovation Ministry Prof Siti Hamisah Tapsir, was established on May 10, 2022 to address the issues pertaining to poor working environment in healthcare industry. Its mandate was to analyze and evaluate reports and recommendations for improving the work culture and human resources management in the public health sector (Harun & Salleduddin, 2022). Hence, this study would examine the influence of working environment towards employee service performance in the Malaysian the Healthcare Industry.

Lastly, the Malaysian Ministry of Health is reviewing its on-call rate of doctors and linking it to their performance appraisal as a way to improve their service performance (Harun & Salleduddin, 2022). Performance appraisal of healthcare employees would affect the level service performance as employees as according to the Code Blue Malaysia survey, it was found that too many key performance indicators (KPIs) and extra services that they have to provide to patients affected the level of service performance of healthcare employees in Malaysia (Iskandar, 2023). Furthermore, a good appraisal system would improve the performance of healthcare service providers and would lead to retention of workers in the healthcare industry ("Good performance should be rewarded", 2023). Hence, this study would examine the influence of performance appraisal towards employee service performance in the Malaysian the healthcare Industry. The purpose of this research is to analyze the likely relationships that may exist between teamwork, training, working environment and performance appraisal with employee service performance in the Malaysian healthcare industry. The results of this research would not only enrich current literature but would also establish awareness and advocate the appropriate policies needed to enhance the employee service performance.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Teamwork

Teamwork is a process that involves forming teams where employees are expected to work coherently towards the realization of organizational goals Kelemba et al. (2017). In the healthcare industry, teamwork refers to the collaboration of several healthcare experts, such as physicians, nurses, allied health professionals, and support workers, in order to provide patients with high-quality treatment. Teamwork is crucial and may have a big influence on how well services are provided (White et al., 2021). Teams of specialists from various specializations, collaborate in the healthcare industry to deliver high-quality patient care. According to the research from Mayo (2020), healthcare employees are more likely to exchange information and communicate efficiently when they operate as a team. By doing so, mistakes can be prevented, all facets of patient care can be integrated, and patients will have a better overall experience. The clear, timely exchange of information is becoming increasingly crucial as the healthcare workforce becomes more dynamic in response to contagious diseases and people come together

without previously having established a shared method of doing the task (Tambo et al., 2021). When healthcare professionals collaborate, they can more efficiently identify and reduce hazards (Albott et al., 2020). By doing so, patient safety can be increased and medical mistakes can be avoided due to fewer redundant tasks are performed, and patient care is not delayed needlessly, hence patients may receive a highly performed healthcare services. Patients are more likely to receive the appropriate therapy at the appropriate time when healthcare professionals collaborate to coordinate care and exchange expertise. Better health results and better patient satisfaction may result from this (Solli et al., 2020). By working as a team, healthcare professionals may benefit from the knowledge, expertise, and experience of one another to make better clinical decisions. Decision making process is an important process for every organization as it could lead to success if the decision is made correctly. Many steps, including planning, scheduling, and controlling, cannot be completed without effective decision-making. Making decisions serves as a choice and has a commitment to the company organization (Sharma et al., 2021). The decision-making process will appear to be more significant in the healthcare industry as the process should be done properly and correctly without any negligence to ensure the positive outcome of patients. As mentioned in the research by Bijani et al. (2021), having good teamwork skills will contribute to good decision-making in medical services; this approach may finally lead to a good service performance for customers. As such, we proposed based on this literature review that:

H1: There is a significant positive relationship between the teamwork and employee service performance in the Malaysian healthcare industry.

2.2 Training

According to Aguinis and Kraiger (2009), training also refers to a systematic approach to learning and development to increase one's performance as an individual, a team, and an organization. Enhancing service performance requires proper training. It provides employees with the information, abilities, and resources required to offer consumers high-quality service performance (Mulyani et al., 2020). It is simple to see how training affects service performance where the better the training, the better the service performance. Training can boost employees' self-assurance and job satisfaction. Employees are more likely to be involved in their work and feel proud of their performance if they believe they possess the information and abilities needed to do their jobs (Arulmani et al.). As a result, employees may offer clients greater service because they are more driven to do so. Organizations may adapt to shifting client demands and expectations with the use of training (Agrawal et al., 2020). Organizations must continuously assess their performance and make adjustments if they intend to stay ahead of the curve. Employees who get training are more likely to adopt a growth mindset, which motivates them to explore novel concepts and methods, try out cutting-edge tools, and keep honing their abilities (Han & Stieha, 2020). Additionally, regular training sessions may also keep employees informed about new rules, practices, and tools that might enhance their effectiveness in providing services (Etkind et al., 2020). Healthcare's first focus is patient safety. Understanding safety regulations and procedures may be improved by training, which raises safety awareness and reduces adverse incidents. Every organization including healthcare that prioritizes providing top-notch customer service must consider the connection between training and service performance. The healthcare industry may enhance their service delivery, which will boost customer happiness and loyalty, by investing in training programs that provide employees with the information and skills they need to do their jobs well (Dandis et al., 2021). Regulations including HIPAA (Health Insurance Portability and Accountability), OSHA (Occupational Safety and Health Administration), and JCAHO (Joint Commission and Accreditation of Healthcare organizations) must be followed by healthcare personnel. Training may make it easier for healthcare personnel to comprehend and follow these rules, creating a workplace that is safer and more compliant (Alhumaid et al., 2021). As such, we proposed based on this literature review that:

H2: There is a significant positive relationship between training and employee service performance in the Malaysian healthcare industry.

2.3 Working Environment

Working environment is defined as the setting, social features, as well as physical conditions wherein people conduct their task (Azman & Zainal, 2022). According to Gomez and Bernet (2019), a positive working environment can eventually improve employee service performance. The healthcare sector may be particularly stressful due to the long hours that healthcare workers put in, the challenging patients and families they encounter, and the frequent handling of life-or-death situations. High levels of stress can cause burnout, lower work satisfaction, and subpar service delivery (Daphna-Tekoah et al., 2020). A supportive work environment in the healthcare sector comprises elements like workplace safety, professional growth opportunities, and work-life balance. Stress levels may be decreased, employees' engagement can be raised, and service performance can be improved with a safe and pleasant working environment (Jang et al., 2020). Besides, a pleasant and encouraging working environment may give employees a feeling of belonging. Employees are more likely to be motivated to work successfully when they feel like they are a member of a team and are working towards shared goals. Having a sense of belonging may boost productivity and improve service performance (Rasool et al., 2021). Moreover, a positive working environment also offers an opportunity to employees for professional development (Chanana, 2021). Employees are more likely to be driven to provide outstanding performance when they believe they have the opportunity to learn and develop in their positions. This determination may result from the accomplishment and sense of growth that come with gaining more knowledge or taking on more responsibility (Werdhiastutie et al., 2020). Parashakti et al., (2022) study on employee performance in Masmitra Hospital Indonesia, found that work environment has a positive and significant effect on employee performance. As a result, healthcare organizations may improve employee service performance by enhancing their working environment. As such, we proposed based on this literature review that:

H3: There is a significant positive relationship between working environment and employee service performance in the Malaysian healthcare industry.

2.4 Performance Appraisal

Performance appraisal is an estimation of how well an employee performs job-related tasks through evaluation processes that include identifying, measuring, influencing and developing job performance of employees in the organization for specified norms and standards for a specific amount of time in order to achieve different goals and objectives (Gupta & Parmar, 2018). According to the research from Diamantidis and Chatzoglou (2019), performance appraisal and employee service performance are closely related. By giving employees feedback on their job performance, highlighting their areas for improvement, and emphasizing their strengths, a well-designed performance appraisal system may aid in improving service performance (Vuong & Nguyen, 2022). Healthcare employees receive feedback on their work performance through performance evaluation. By understanding their strengths and shortcomings and identifying their areas for growth, healthcare workers may use this feedback to optimize their job performance and patient care. Performance assessment can assist healthcare organizations in identifying opportunities for patient care enhancements, such as enhancing patient safety, lowering prescription mistakes, or enhancing professional healthcare communication. Healthcare organizations may take steps to address these areas of improvement and raise the standard of care they offer (Domer et al., 2021). Healthcare organizations may use performance appraisal systems to identify training requirements, create strategies for performance enhancement, and reward exceptional personnel (Kihama & Wainaina, 2019). Healthcare organizations can identify healthcare workers who require more training or development to enhance their job performance and patient care through performance appraisal. Healthcare organizations may increase the knowledge and abilities of their healthcare staff, improving patient outcomes and service performance, by providing training and development opportunities. Performance appraisal can also assist healthcare organizations in identifying and rewarding top-performing healthcare personnel. Top-performing healthcare professionals can act as role models for their colleagues and inspire others to perform even better. This might result in greater service performance overall (Singh et al., 2022). As such, we proposed based on this literature review that:

H4: There is a significant positive relationship between performance appraisal and employee service performance in the Malaysian healthcare industry.

Figure 1: The Conceptual Framework

3. Research Method

3.1 Sample

Questionnaires were administered online to 200 healthcare employees in Penang and Selangor Malaysia as these states have one of the highest medical tourism. Non-probability, convenience sampling method was used in the collection of the data.

3.2 Questionnaire Design

The questionnaire had two sections. The first section of the questionnaire was the demographic profile consisting of gender, race, age, highest education level, monthly income level and job position. The second section of the questionnaire were questions related to the independent variables and the dependent variable of the study. A ten-item scale to measure teamwork adapted from Lower et al (2017) was applied in the questionnaire. Next, an eight-item scale for training was adapted from Bartlett (2001) and a five-item scale to measure working environment was adapted from Vaughan, (2021) and Kinne, (2022). A five-item scale for performance appraisal was adapted from Evan (1978), while a seven-item scale for employee service performance was adapted from Liao and Chuang (2004). Each of the variable in this study was measured using a 5 point Likert scale ranging from (1) “strongly disagree” to (5) “strongly agree”.

3.3 Data Analysis

Using SPSS software, the study found that the Cronbach’s Alpha value generated from 200 responses was 0.913. The data was regarded reliable because the Cronbach’s Alpha value was greater than 0.7. Cronbach’s Alpha for each variable are also above 0.7; teamwork (0.714), training (0.702), working environment (0.752), performance appraisal (0.789) and employee service performance (0.701). As for the normality test, the Z-score calculation for normality was -3.197 which is within $-3.29 < Z > 3.29$. Furthermore, the linearity test assumption was met based on randomized pattern of the scatter plot.

3.4 Demographics of Respondents

The respondents comprised of 55 percent male and 45 percent female. In terms of race, about 52.5 percent of the respondents were Chinese, 16 percent were Malays, 16.5 percent others and 15 percent were Indians. Age wise, 48 percent of the respondents were between the age group of 21 to 30 years old, followed by 19.5 percent were between the age group of 31 to 40 years old, while 16.5 percent were between the ages of 41 to 50 years old and lastly 16 percent were between the age of 51 to 60 years old. 52.5 percent of the respondents have a bachelor's degree as their highest qualification. Income wise, 46 percent earned a monthly income between RM4,001 – RM5,000, while 30 percent earned a monthly income of more than RM5,000. Lastly 52.5 percent of respondents were from the managerial level and 35.5 percent were from operational level. Table 1 shows the respondents' demographic profile.

Table 1: Respondents' Demographic Profile

Demographic features		Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	110	55.0
	Female	90	45.0
Race	Malay	32	16.0
	Chinese	105	52.5
	Indian	30	15.0
	Others	33	16.5
Age	21 - 30 years old	96	48.0
	31 - 40 years old	39	19.5
	41 - 50 years old	33	16.5
	51 - 60 years old	32	16.0
Highest Education Level	Diploma/O levels/IGSCE	70	35.0
	Bachelor's Degree	105	52.5
	Master's Degree	21	10.5
	Others	4	2.0
Monthly Income Level	< RM3,000	20	10.0
	RM3,001 – RM4,000	28	14.0
	RM4,001 – RM5,000	92	46.0
	> RM5,000	60	30.0
Job Position	Operational Level	71	35.5
	Managerial Level	105	52.5
	Executive Level	24	12.0

4. Result and Discussion

4.1 Pearson Correlation

The relationships between teamwork, training, working environment and performance appraisal was tested with employee service performance in the Pearson Correlation test. The results indicate that, teamwork was 0.578, training was 0.635, working environment was 0.617 and performance appraisal was 0.582. Table 2 shows the results of the Pearson Correlation test.

Table 2. Results of the Pearson Correlation Test

		Employee Service Performance	Teamwork	Training	Working Environment	Performance Appraisal
Firm Performance	Pearson Correlation	1	.578	.635	.617	.582
	Sig. (2 tailed)					
	N	200	200	200	200	200

4.2 Multiple Regression Analysis

According to Table 3 below, the model summary tells the strength of relationship between dependent variable and independent variables. R-square and Durbin-Watson value would be interpreted in this analysis. Firstly, the R-square indicated that the total variation of dependent variable (employee service performance) in this model can be explained by the independent variables (teamwork, training, working environment, performance appraisal). It shows that 0.542 (54.2%) of employee service performance would be explained by teamwork, training, working environment and performance appraisal. Secondly, the Durbin-Watson value, which is within 1-3, would indicate that there is no autocorrelation problem among the errors. The Durbin-Watson value for this study is 2.150 which is within the range. Table 3 shows the model summary.

Table 3. Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of Estimation	Durbin Watson
1	.736 ^a	.542	.533	.41299	2.150

According to ANOVA analysis, the p-value is <.001, hence, the model is statistically significant. As such, the model is considered fit for further analysis. The F value of 57.986, which indicates that the conceptual model is strongly significant, and the variation is not totally accounted by possibility. Table 4 shows the analysis of variance (ANOVA) in this study.

Table 4. Analysis of variance (ANOVA) in this study

Model		ANOVA ^a				
		Sum of Squares	DF	Mean Square	F	Significance
1	Regression	39.560	4	9.890	57.986	<.001 ^b
	Residual	33.429	196	.171		
	Total	72.989	200			

The coefficients in table 5 reveal that H1, H2 and H3 are accepted as teamwork, training and working environment have significant values of less than 0.05 while H4 was rejected as performance appraisal had a significance value of more than 0.05. Next, since the research uses primary data, the B (Beta) value of unstandardized coefficients would be analysed. In this study, the working environment variable carries the highest B value. It is a positive value of 0.306, which means it has a more crucial positive relationship with the dependent variable (employee service performance). Lastly, the Tolerance and VIF value in collinearity statistics would be evaluated. The tolerance value that is lower or equal to 10 indicates that there is no multicollinearity problem. On the other hand, VIF value that is between the values of 1 to 5 is regarded as moderately correlated. Hence, it is demonstrated that the study is free of multicollinearity problem and the variables are moderately correlated to each other. Table 5 shows the results of the coefficients.

Table 5. Results of the coefficients

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients Beta	t	Sig	Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std. Error				Tolerance	VIF
(Constant)	.669	.209		3.201	.002		
Teamwork	.239	.064	.251	3.722	<.001	.512	1.951
Training	.175	.073	.186	2.390	.018	.386	2.587
Working Environment	.306	.055	.345	5.531	<.001	.512	1.951
Performance Appraisal	.101	.065	.113	1.554	.122	.439	2.278

Table 6. Summary of the hypotheses result

		Significance	Results	Gradient (Beta, β)
H1	There is a significant positive relationship between the teamwork and employee service performance in the Malaysian healthcare industry	<.001	Accepted	.239
H2	There is a significant positive relationship between training and employee service performance in the Malaysian healthcare industry	.018	Accepted	.175
H3	There is a significant positive relationship between working environment and employee service performance in the Malaysian healthcare industry	<.001	Accepted	.306
H4	There is a significant positive relationship between performance appraisal and employee service performance in the Malaysian healthcare industry..	.122	Rejected	.101

5. Conclusion

The results of this study have shown that teamwork has a significant positive association with employee service performance in the Malaysian healthcare industry because its significance value was less than 0.05. Besides that, it has a B value of 0.239, which signifies that it would positively affect employee service performance. It means that the more the healthcare industry engages in teamwork, the employee service performance would also improve. The result of this study is similar with the studies carried out by Bijani et al. (2021), Sharma et al. (2021) and Solli et al. (2020) whereby teamwork positively affects employee service performance. Furthermore, training was found to have a significant association to employee service performance in the Malaysian healthcare industry because its significance value was lower than 0.05. Besides that, it has a B value of 0.175 signifies that it would positively affect employee service performance. In other words, the more training provided, the better the employee service performance in the healthcare industry. The result was similar with the studies carried out by Alhumaid et al.(2021),

Dandis et al., (2021) and Etkind et al. (2020). Finally, this study have revealed that working environment has a significant positive association with employee service performance in the Malaysian healthcare industry because its significance value was less than 0.05. This is similar to the studies by Parashakti et al. (2022), Chanana (2021). Rasool et al. (2021) and Werdhiastutie et al. (2020). Further it has a B value of 0.306, which means it plays a prominent role it its effect on employee service performance in the healthcare industry in Malaysia.

There was no significant relationship found between performance appraisal and employee service performance in the healthcare industry in Malaysia because its significance value was 0.122 which is higher than 0.05. Besides that, it had the lowest B value among other variables (0.101), which signifies that it barely affects employee service performance. The result is contrary to Vuong and Nguyen, (2022) study that performance appraisal affects employee service performance, however the difference in results might be due to the need to identify the areas in the performance appraisal that any affect employee service performance in healthcare. This can be areas such frequency, feedback, standards or performance appraisal polistics that may exists (Hameed et al, 2023)

This study has highlighted the importance of teamwork, training and working environment on employee service performance in the Malaysian healthcare industry. As such, the practical contribution of this study is the need to foster teamwork, training and positive working environment in the Malaysian healthcare industry. Training is essential in the healthcare industry to improve the quality of care, for regulatory compliance, skill development, crisis management during a crisis and the spread of contagious disease, patient safety, and to be able to adapt to technology integration. On the other hand, teamwork is a necessity in the health care industry to provide a holistic patient care, enhance problem solving and provide effective and efficient services. While, health care employees need to be in a healthy and safe environment with their mental health and well-being being a priority while providing quality patient experience. As such, it is important for the survival of the healthcare industry that contributes to Malaysian medical tourism. MOH must ensure that policies are in place and in line with international standards that can elevate service performance of employees in the healthcare industry. MOH must continually evaluate and enhance the quality of the services in the healthcare industry; healthcare service providers might put quality improvement initiatives into place. Regular audits, performance reviews, and employee and patient feedback may be a part of these activities (Pastorino et al., 2019).

Based on the findings of the study, in order to ensure that there is a robust healthcare system that helps in the prevention, early detection, and effective management of diseases, which will contributing to the overall public health and subsequently reducing the burden of illness on the population, employees need to be provided proper training. They must also be able to work together and have a proper working environment so that service performance will improve. Researchers could use this study as a comparative study to further investigate the variables and examine the generalizability of the model to other sample population.

6. Limitation and Future Research

There are a few limitation in this study, however, these limitations can be used to conduct future studies. Firstly, future studies may conduct a comparative studies with the healthcare industry of neighboring countries of Malaysia such as Thailand, Indonesia, Philippines, Brunei and Singapore so that Malaysia can identify best practices and innovative approaches to healthcare delivery. This can include successful strategies to enhance employee services in public health, hospital management and disease prevention. A longitudinal study can also be conducted and variables such leadership may be included as this variable may also affect employee service performance especially during a health crisis (Alsadaan,2023). The results of this research will contribute to the existing knowledge on the importance of teamwork, training and working environment on employee service performance in the Malaysian healthcare industry. The results of this study will promote the appropriate policies needed in organizations for the enhancement of employee service performance. The intervention of the Malaysian government and policy makers as well as professional bodies in creating awareness and providing assistance on the implementation of appropriate policies is necessary for the sustainability of the Malaysian healthcare industry.

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